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CURRENCY FUTURES IN INDIA: AN INTRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT

The introduction of currency futures in India has passed a journey of almost one and a half year and many changes have been implemented in the trading system in this regard. The main theme of this paper is to assess the speed in which the growth of currency futures in India has accelerated. It also aims at analysing the volatility of the currency futures. In order to study the growth of the currency futures, the number of contracts traded and open interest at NSE and MCX have been inclusively compared. Attempt has been made to check whether the daily returns of the NSE and MCX on currency futures are normally distributed. For this purpose the changes in the daily value of Rupee as compared to Dollar has been calculated for every month seperately and the data have been used for the Kolmogorov Smirnov Test to test the hypothesis that the returns are normally distributed. With the measure of skewness and kurtosis it has been found that the returns are normally distributed and, thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. The currency futures have received a good response from the investors as well as the hedgers. initially currency futures were started for USD-INR contracts but recently trading in Euro-INR, Yen-INR and Pound-INR contracts have been introduced in January 2010. Average turnover of these instruments in the National Stock Exchange and MCX Stock Exchange (MCX-SX) in December was nine times higher than a year earlier. These exchanges are currently clocking an average daily turnover of over Rs 20,000 crore in currency products while it was just Rs 2,400 crore in January last year. The risk involved is comparatively low in this case and currency futures has proved to be a good tool for hedging the risk involved in the currency of a country (currency risk). It is hoped that the currency futures market will develop more faster and it will be a good choice for all the market participants in the near future and it will find its way in the Indian economy.

KEYWORDS: currency futures, open interest, volume traded, currency risk.

I. INTRODUCTION

“By far the most significant event in finance during the past decade has been the extraordinary development and expansion of financial derivatives. These instruments enhance the ability to differentiate risk and allocate it to those investors most able and willing to take it – a process that has undoubtedly improved national productivity growth and standard of living.”

.....Alan Greenspan (Former Chairman, Board of Governors of the US Federal System)

Currency Futures means a standardised foreign exchange derivative contract traded on a recognized stock exchange to buy or sell one currency against another on a specified future date,

at a price specified on the date of contract, but does not include a forward contract. Currency Futures market means the market in which currency futures are traded. Currency futures were first created at the Chicago Mercantile Exchange (CME) in 1972. In India, NSE was the first stock exchange, permitted by the SEBI, to set up its separate currency derivatives segment. Standardized currency futures trading started on 28th August, 2008 in NSE with the following features:

- a. Only USD-INR contracts were allowed to be traded.
- b. The size of each contract shall be USD 1000.
- c. The contracts shall be quoted and settled in Indian Rupees.
- d. The maturity of the contracts shall not exceed 12 months.
- e. The settlement price shall be the Reserve Bank's Reference Rate on the last trading day.
- f. Only Indian residents shall be eligible for the contracts.

Similarly, the BSE and MCX started trading the currency futures from 1st and 7th October, 2008 respectively. The major objective of using derivatives is hedging the risk (Anand & Kaushik, 2004). One of the major benefits by the start of this trading was to the investors that earlier only those companies, who were exposed to currency risk, were allowed to hedge their risk in the currency forwards but the introduction of the currency futures allowed all investors to trade in currencies. However, a successful year of trading led the RBI and SEBI allow the currency futures in three new pairs, viz; Yen-INR, Pound-INR and Euro-INR, thus allowing the investors more relevant contracts for hedging.

II. OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY

“It has been said in the past that derivatives are kind of a side show, where the main event takes place in the money and capital markets. One could attend the side show without taking part in the main event and vice-versa. With respect to derivative and money/capital markets, that is simply not true today. Derivatives are so widely used that even if one has no intention of using them, it is important to understand how they are used by others and what effects, positive and negative; they could have on money and capital markets.”

.....Peter L. Bernstein (Against the Gods)

The futures market holds a great importance in the economy and, therefore, it becomes imperative that we analyse this important market and seek answers to a few basic questions. The main theme of the study is to assess the progress of the currency futures in India with a compact view over the volatility of the currency futures. In order to study the growth of the currency futures, the number of contracts traded and open interest at NSE and MCX have been inclusively compared. A correlation between the two was calculated and the result depicted that they have a significant relationship with a correlation coefficient of 0.83 in case of NSE. A plot of that correlation is shown in Figure 1.

Attempt has also been made to check whether the daily returns of the NSE and MCX on currency futures are normally distributed and the data have been used for the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test to test the hypothesis that the returns are normally distributed. Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test is a non-parametric test and it is used to determine whether the distribution is homogeneous. With the measure of skewness and kurtosis it has been found that the returns are normally distributed and, thus, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The hypothesis tested in the study is as follows:

H_0 : The returns of the currency futures are normally distributed.

H_1 : The returns of the currency futures are not normally distributed.

FIGURE 1: PLOTTED GRAPH OF CORRELATION BETWEEN OPEN INTEREST AND CONTRACTS TRADED AT NSE

III. QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS

The growth of the currency futures in India has been assessed by measuring the growth in two variables which are open interest and contracts traded. A correlation between the two was calculated and the result depicted that they have a significant relationship with a correlation coefficient of 0.83 in case of NSE.

**TABLE 2: CORRELATION BETWEEN OPEN INTEREST AND CONTRACTS
TRADED IN NSE**

Linear Correlation
Number of points = 320
Correlation coefficient (r) = 0.8324
95% confidence interval: 0.7953 to 0.8632
Coefficient of determination (r squared) = 0.6928
Test: Is r significantly different than zero?
The two-tailed P value is < 0.0001, considered extremely significant.

The growth of the open interest and contracts traded are explained below:

I. OPEN INTEREST

Open interest is the total number of outstanding contracts that are held by the market participants at the end of the day. It is also considered as the number of futures contracts that have not yet been exercised, expired or fulfilled by delivery. It is often used to confirm the trends and trends reversals for futures markets. It measures the flow of money into the futures market. A seller and a buyer forms one contract and hence in order to determine the total open interest in the market we need to know either the total of buyers or the sellers and not the sum of both. The open interest position that is reported each day represents the increase or decrease in the number of contracts for that day. An increasing open interest means that the new money is flowing in the marketplace and the present trend will continue. If the open interest is declining it implies that the market is liquidating and the prevailing price trend is coming to an end. The leveling off of open interest following a sustained price advance is often an early warning of the end to an uptrending or bull market. The interpretations which can be made on the basis of the open interest may be shown with the help of the following table:

Price	Open Interest	Interpretation
Rising	Rising	Market is Strong
Rising	Falling	Market is weakening
Falling	Rising	Market is Weak
Falling	Falling	Market is Strengthening

Figure 2 shows the daily movement in the open interest of currency futures in both NSE and MCX. It depicts that the open interest in both NSE and MCX have been increasing with a steady speed since the currency futures are been traded. The open interest in the NSE was 406200 on 31st Dec. 2009 as compared to 16332 on 28th Aug. 2008 and that on MCX it was 425451 on 31st Dec. 2009 as compared to 17331 on 7th Oct. 2008. It can be seen that in terms of the open interest, the growth of the MCX is more as compared to the NSE.

FIGURE 2

The trend as depicted by figure 1 it is found that the growth of open interest in both NSE and MCX was down during March 2009 to August 2009 which is the indicator that it was affected by the global recession experienced by the Indian economy. Figure 3, which shows the open interest at the end of each month, also depicts that there was a fall in the open interest during the period of January-July 2009. Hence, it can be said that this slackening in trade was due to the global recession. However, the market has recovered itself and a good growth is being experienced.

FIGURE 3

II. CONTRACTS TRADED

The number of contracts traded on a stock exchange shows the total volume of contracts traded. An increase in the number of contracts traded on an stock exchange expresses the growth of trade in that particular stock exchange for a particular currency future. The number contracts traded in the NSE increased to 1444150 contracts on 31st Dec. 2009 from 65798 contracts on 28th Aug. 2008, and from 59952 contracts on 7th Oct. 2008 to 1556411 contracts on 31st Dec. 2009 in the MCX. Figure 4 clearly depicts the growing trend in the daily volumes traded in both NSE and MCX. It can also be noticed over here that the number of contracts traded in MCX have been more than that traded in the NSE.

FIGURE 4

III. MONTHLY TURNOVER

The monthly turnover of both the stock exchanges (NSE and MCX) have also experienced an upward trend in the year 2009 with a total of Rs. 48395 crore in Jan. 2009 and Rs. 319195 crore in Nov. 2009. Figure 5 depicts the clear picture of the currently moving trend in both the stock exchanges. This too says that the currency futures trading at MCX is growing faster than that at NSE.

FIGURE 5

IV. NORMALITY IN THE DAILY CHANGES IN VALUE OF RUPEE

The distribution of the changes in the value of Rupee is not symmetric as the skewness is not zero in any case. Presence of positive skewness in Dec. 2008, Feb. 2009, Mar. 2009, Apr. 2009, June 2009, July 2009, Aug. 2009, Sept. 2009, Nov. 2009 and Dec. 2009 means that the distribution has a right tail and the negative skewness in rest of the months means that the distribution has a left tail. In case of kurtosis, it can be concluded that the distribution was normal only during May 2009 and during the rest of the period it was not normally distributed. A detailed statistic is given in the Table 1.

TABLE 1: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF DAILY CHANGES IN THE VALUE OF RUPEE (MONTH-WISE)

Period	No. of Obs.	Mean	S.D.	Min	Max	Skewness	Kurtosis
Sept. 08	20	0.1575	0.3774	-0.92	0.69	-1.28	2.32
Oct. 08	15	0.1433	0.4404	-0.58	0.73	-0.2846	-1.18
Nov. 08	17	0.0518	0.6189	-1.44	1.22	-0.3942	1.04
Dec. 08	20	-0.082	0.5413	-1.1	1.1	0.4118	0.24
Jan. 09	19	0.0153	0.2841	-0.52	0.43	-0.2313	-1.15
Feb. 09	16	0.105	0.2712	-0.21	0.69	1.0553	0.14
Mar. 09	18	-0.0444	0.3574	-0.63	0.54	0.008	-0.17
Apr. 09	15	-0.0053	0.3327	-0.62	0.53	0.0068	-0.67
May. 09	19	-0.1258	0.4296	-1.38	0.49	-1.2914	3.04
Jun. 09	21	0.042	0.2734	-0.38	0.53	0.0373	-0.82
Jul. 09	22	0.0032	0.2793	-0.56	0.71	0.464	0.91
Aug. 09	19	0.0532	0.2055	-0.33	0.41	0.0656	-0.37
Sept. 09	18	-0.0383	0.185	-0.39	0.33	0.2875	-0.38
Oct. 09	17	-0.0394	0.3477	-0.56	0.4	-0.1591	-1.71
Nov. 09	19	-0.0295	0.2227	-0.41	0.54	0.4711	1.15
Dec. 09	20	0.0115	0.1108	-0.2	0.23	0.0388	-0.06

Contrary to the statistical results based on skewness and kurtosis, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test says that the distribution is normal in every case. The detailed results are given in the Table 2.

TABLE 2: ONE-SAMPLE KOLMOGOROV-SMIRNOV TEST

	Dec. 09	Nov. 09	Oct. 09	Sept. 09	Aug. 09	Jul. 09	Jun. 09	May 09	Apr.0 9	Mar. 09	Feb. 09	Jan. 09	Dec. 08	Nov. 08	Oct. 08	Sept. 08
N	20	19	17	18	19	22	21	19	15	18	16	19	20	17	15	20
Normal Mean Parameters ^a , ^b	.0115	- .0295	- .0394	- .0383	.0532	.0032	.0419	- .1258	-.0053	- .0444	.1050	.0153	- .0820	.0518	.1433	.1575
Std. Deviation	.1108 0	.2227 0	.3477 3	.1849 7	.2054 8	.2792 9	.2733 6	.4296 4	.33273	.3574 1	.2712 4	.2840 8	.5412 9	.6189 1	.4404 2	.3774 1
Most Extreme Differences																
Absolute	.111	.133	.184	.186	.108	.112	.133	.176	.112	.106	.213	.133	.176	.132	.142	.163
Positive	.111	.133	.159	.186	.108	.112	.133	.087	.112	.106	.213	.133	.176	.122	.104	.093
Negative	-.089	-.130	-.184	-.121	-.076	-.071	-.130	-.176	-.094	-.088	-.123	-.121	-.072	-.132	-.142	-.163
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	.494	.578	.758	.790	.472	.527	.608	.768	.436	.451	.853	.582	.789	.544	.552	.730
Asymp. Sig. (2- tailed)	.967	.892	.613	.561	.979	.944	.854	.597	.991	.987	.461	.888	.562	.929	.921	.661

a. Test distribution is Normal.

b. Calculated from data

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The Indian currency futures market has experienced an impressive growth since its introduction. The upward trend of the volumes and open interest for currency futures in both NSE and MCX explains the whole story in detail. The growth was only the reason for the introduction of three other currency futures in January this year. In the coming future it is expected that the market participants will find some more currency futures introduced into the market. Currently on 26th March, 2010 the SEBI allowed the United Stock Exchange of India to launch currency futures. It became the fourth currency future exchange after NSE, BSE and MCX. The two exchanges (NSE and MCX) are currently clocking an average daily turnover of over Rs 20,000 crore in currency products while it was just Rs 2,400 crore in January last year. It can be thus concluded that the currency futures market will get more success in the coming future and the economy and the risk hedgers will definitely be benefited from this trade. The correlation test also explained that the relationship between the open interest and traded volumes is very much significant and that the change in the value of currency is normally distributed thus illustrating that the risk is minimum in the currency futures contracts. The risk involved is comparatively low in this case and currency futures has proved to be a good tool for hedging the risk involved in the currency of a country (currency risk). It is hoped that the currency futures market will develop faster and it will be a good choice for all the market participants in the near future and it will find its way in the Indian economy.

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